

Mercury Science Goals, Objectives, and Investigations

Mercury Exploration Assessment Group (MExAG)

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The *MExAG Science Goals, Objectives, and Investigations* document is the first of three MExAG goals documents: Science, Technology, and Community. This document is recommended to be cited as: “*The Mercury Exploration Assessment Group Science Goals, Objectives, and Investigations, MExAG (2025). Version 1.0, XX pp., <insert LPI Link>*”.

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the science goals of the MExAG community for understanding and exploring Mercury. The intended audiences for the document are: (1) NASA, as a means for communicating the community-driven goals, and (2) the planetary science community, as a mechanism of sharing knowledge about important themes for understanding and exploring Mercury. This document will be updated every three years, to maintain relevance and utility. Community members wishing to provide input can do so at any time by emailing mexag.sc@gmail.com.

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Overview

The document is structured into *goals* and *objectives*, with *objectives* broken into several more-specific *sub-objectives*. The *goals* are the high-level outcomes to be achieved and should remain fairly stable over time. The *objectives* identify strategies to achieve the goals. The *objectives* are intended to be broad, so that the ways in which they can be conducted are not overly constrained. Once the Technology Goals Document has been published, the intention is to revise the Science Goals document to include specific *investigations*. These investigations will describe specific missions or studies that could be undertaken to achieve an objective. *Goals* and *objectives* are listed in the outline below.

Goal 1 is focused on how Mercury can be used to address scientific questions about our solar system and beyond. It demonstrates how **Mercury is a keystone for understanding the origin and evolution of our solar system**, the planets within it, and the processes that affect them.

Goals 2–4 are more directly focused on **understanding the evolution of Mercury** itself. These goals include all aspects of Mercury's formation and evolution, and are intended to be a comprehensive resource for proposers.

Outline

Document	Goals	Objectives
Science	1) Establish Mercury's context in our solar system and beyond	1.1) Use Mercury's uniqueness as a compositional and physical end-member to constrain the formation of the solar system
		1.2) Apply our knowledge of Mercury to understand other planetary bodies and vice versa
		1.3) Inform our understanding of rocky exoplanets
	2) Understand the origins of Mercury, from accretion to solidification	2.1) Investigate compositional building blocks
		2.2) Explore formation scenarios
		2.3) Understand global differentiation/evolution
	3) Characterize Mercury's evolution since solidification	3.1) Study past geological processes
		3.2) Understand processes behind the chemical and mineralogical diversity of the crust
		3.3) Investigate the origin and evolution of the polar deposits
		3.4) Explore the history of the intrinsic magnetic field
		3.5) Infer long-term effects of variations in exospheric and magnetospheric source and loss mechanisms
	4) Investigate processes currently ongoing at Mercury	4.1) Characterize present-day geologic activity
		4.2) Investigate magnetospheric dynamics
		4.3) Understand exospheric and magnetospheric source and loss processes

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Executive Summary

The ongoing advances in cosmochemistry and planet formation dynamics places Mercury firmly **at the center of understanding how our solar system formed**. Its composition is likely a key geochemical end-member in the solar system, but it is as yet unsampled. Measuring its composition would not only revolutionize our understanding of Mercury's formation, but also shed light on the makeup of the Earth and other planets, the origin of life-essential volatiles in the inner solar system, and how planets accreted in the early protoplanetary disk.

As the **closest planet to the Sun**, Mercury provides a unique vantage point to study a range of key planetary processes, including: accretion in the protoplanetary disk, past and current cratering rates, space weathering, and volatile delivery to the inner planets. Its proximity to the Sun also provides a unique window into many exoplanets, a substantial fraction of which orbit as close, or closer, to their host stars than Mercury. Due to its proximity to the Sun, Mercury formed in an oxygen-poor, carbon-rich environment, distinct from all other terrestrial planets. Many exoplanets also formed in such low-oxygen conditions, making Mercury uniquely suited to understanding their formation and evolution. **Mercury is truly an 'exoplanet in our backyard'**.

The **large (relative) size of Mercury's core** is also unique within the solar system. The core produces a global magnetic field that leads to complex interactions between the Sun and the planet's surface. This interaction provides insights into the dynamics of planetary magnetospheres, exospheres, and space weathering.

Surprisingly, **there is thought to be more water ice on Mercury than on the Moon**. As with the Moon, it has been found in permanently shadowed regions of craters at Mercury's poles, but in Mercury's case, there are actually large areas of exposed ice. How and when this ice formed is unknown, but it is clearly a unique record of volatile delivery and deposition in the inner solar system.

By advancing the understanding of Mercury, key contributions to many of the Priority Science Questions identified in the National Academies Origins, Worlds, and Life Decadal Survey* will be made, including: **Q1)** Evolution of the protoplanetary disk, **Q3)** Origin of the Earth and inner solar system bodies, **Q4)** Impacts and dynamics, **Q5)** Solid body interiors and surfaces, **Q6)** Solid body atmosphere, exospheres, magnetospheres and climate evolution, and **Q12)** Exoplanets.

* *National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2023. Origins, Worlds, and Life: A Decadal Strategy for Planetary Science and Astrobiology 2023-2032. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26522>.*

Abbreviations

CSFD - crater size frequency distribution
CMB - core mantle boundary
ESD - electron stimulated desorption
EUV - extreme ultraviolet
FAC - field-aligned current
fO₂ - oxygen fugacity
FR - flux rope
fS - sulfur fugacity
FTE - flux transfer event
GRAIL - Gravity Recovery And Interior Laboratory (mission)
HMR - high magnesium region
ICME - interplanetary coronal mass ejection
IMF - interplanetary magnetic field
IW - Iron-wüstite oxygen buffer
IR - infrared
JWST - James Webb Space Telescope
KPLO - Korea Pathfinder Lunar Orbiter (mission)
LCROSS - Lunar CRater Observation and Sensing Satellite (mission)
LRM - low-reflectance material
MASCS - Mercury Atmospheric and Surface Composition Spectrometer (instrument)
MDIS - Mercury Dual Imaging System (instrument)
MDM - Mercury Dust Monitor (instrument)
MERTIS - MErcury Radiometer and Thermal Infrared Spectrometer (instrument)
Mio - Mercury Magnetospheric Orbiter (mission)
MORE - Mercury Orbiter Radio-science Experiment (instrument)
MPO - Mercury Planetary Orbiter (spacecraft)
MESSENGER - MErcury Surface, Space ENvironment, GEochemistry and Ranging (mission)
NEO - near-Earth orbit
PSD - photon stimulated desorption
PSR - permanently shadowed region
SEP - solar energetic particle
SIMBIO-SYS - Spectrometer and Imaging for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (instrument)
UVVS - Ultraviolet and Visible Spectrometer (instrument)
VISTIR - visible-to-thermal infrared
VNIR - visible-to-near-Infrared
XRF - X-ray fluorescence
XRS - X-Ray Spectrometer (instrument)

1. Establish Mercury's context in our solar system and beyond

1.1 Use Mercury's uniqueness as a compositional and physical end-member to constrain the formation of the solar system

a) *Cosmochemistry: Is Mercury the missing piece?*

The planets formed in a dynamic environment that was chemically and isotopically heterogeneous (Burkhardt et al., 2019). Subsequent migration of the giant planets scattered and mixed these heterogeneities in the inner solar system (Walsh et al., 2011). It is clear from isotopic data that the Earth and other planets are mixtures of various solar system building blocks, and that one of those components is unsampled, and lies closer to the Sun than the Earth. This component must be enriched in S-process isotopes, but is not present in our current collection of meteorites (Render et al., 2017; Burkhardt et al., 2021). Mercury (and Venus) offer the best opportunity to characterize this key solar system component, as they should contain more of it than the Earth. To quantify the building blocks of the Earth and the other terrestrial planets, including how they received life-essential volatiles, detailed chemical and isotopic analysis of material sunward of the Earth is essential. Isotopic analysis of Mercury's surface, whether in-situ or via sample return, would be uniquely suited for this purpose, as it is the innermost planet and should provide the purest sample of the missing component (Render et al., 2017; Burkhardt et al., 2021). **How the solar system formed cannot be fully established until a geochemical analysis of a Mercury sample is obtained.**

b) *Dynamics of the protoplanetary disk: Why is Mercury so small and so dense?*

Mercury is the smallest terrestrial planet, yet dynamical models generally predict that a larger planet should form at Mercury's orbit of 0.4 AU (Nesvorný et al., 2021). One hypothesis is that Mercury was larger in the past, but some of its silicate portion was removed by one or more collisions (Benz et al., 1988). This scenario would explain the large core, relative to the mantle, which leads to its extremely high density. Alternatively, Mercury may have formed from a distinctly Fe-metal-rich environment in the disk, and this scenario may explain both the large core and small overall size (Ebel and Stewart, 2018). Distinguishing between the various formation scenarios would provide key insights into conditions in the protoplanetary disk, including the dynamics of dust aggregation and larger protoplanetary collisions. Different dynamical models can be constrained by chemical and isotopic measurements of Mercury's surface material, including the geochronology of planet accretion, core segregation, and crustal growth (Helfrich et al., 2019). **Understanding Mercury's formation provides key constraints on the dynamics of the early inner solar system, not obtainable from any other planet.**

1.2 Apply our knowledge of Mercury to understand other planetary bodies and vice versa

a) *Observed surface geology*

Mercury is the archetype of a one-plate planet that has undergone secular interior cooling, dominated as it is with major shortening structures (e.g., Strom et al., 1975). However, there are tectonic

parallels in the solar system. For example, there are major shortening belts on Earth (e.g., Mouthereau et al., 2013) and Venus (Solomon et al., 1991), and the isolated thrust-fault-related landforms in the martian southern uplands bear a close morphological resemblance to Mercury's "lobate scarps" (Watters et al., 2000). Further, the martian uplands and lunar highlands display morphological similarities to the heavily cratered intercrater plains on Mercury (Oberbeck et al., 1977; Denevi et al., 2018). In a similar vein, volcanic processes drive the growth and evolution of terrestrial planet crusts (Taylor and McLennan, 2009), and volcanism at Mercury provides a window into early planet-formation processes, in particular, accretion so near to the Sun. Mercury and the Moon provide the only examples in our solar system where these processes can be observed without the destructive processes of tectonic recycling or secondary chemical weathering.

Mercury has widespread volatile species on the surface (Kerber et al., 2009; Blewett et al., 2011; Chabot et al., 2016; Nittler et al., 2020). The scale of pyroclastic vents and associated deposits is more substantial on Mercury than on the Moon, suggesting a greater eruption energy, likely driven by a greater concentration of volatiles species (Thomas et al., 2015). However, this goes against previous expectations that Mercury would be volatile-depleted due to its proximity to the Sun (Albarède, 2009; McCubbin et al., 2012).

A fuller understanding of the geological history and landforms on Mercury will help to inform future studies of Mars, Venus, and the Moon. Similarly, establishing in detail the volcanic history of Mercury will provide key insights into the evolution of Mercury's volatile inventory. In particular, detailed mapping combined with models of melt production and eruption will be critical for determining how Mercury's volcanic crust formed, especially in the first few hundred million years (for which there is no recognized evidence preserved in the intercrater plains). Doing so will shed new light on how terrestrial planetary crusts are formed in general.

b) Impact cratering record and flux

The impact flux to the terrestrial planets and the Moon is thought to be sourced from three major populations: leftover planetesimals, asteroids, and comets, whose relative contribution is uncertain and is affected by many factors (Bottke et al., 2002). **Understanding the contribution of these three sources of impactors to Mercury will provide important constraints on the bombardment history of the inner solar system.** Geochemical studies of either in situ or returned samples could be used to constrain early bombardment, by measuring the concentration of highly siderophile elements (as done for the Earth, Moon, and Mars) (Righter, 2003). Additionally, observational studies and theoretical studies of small-body populations (e.g., Davis et al., 2002), as well as comparative studies of impactor populations amongst the bodies of the inner solar system (Fassett et al., 2011), are essential to piece together a complete story of past and present impactor populations and the cratering record of the inner solar system.

The earliest bombardment may have delivered a large amount of material to Mercury, altering its primordial crustal composition through vertical mixing of materials (Rivera-Valentin and Barr, 2014). Large collisions could also have played an important role in shaping both the internal evolution of the planet

(Ebel and Stewart, 2018) and initiated major crustal resurfacing events (Denevi et al., 2013; Marchi et al., 2013). **Mercury provides an end-member for studying cratering and crater-degradation processes due to its relatively high impact velocity, surface temperatures, and distance from the asteroid belt.** One aim is to understand the role of large collisions in shaping Mercury's composition and internal structure. Images and geophysical datasets (e.g., topography and gravity) have been used to identify the number, sizes, and ages of large (typically degraded) basins on Mercury (Fassett et al., 2012; Orgel et al., 2020). These analyses have shed light on the early population of planetesimals and protoplanets in the solar system that would have collided with proto-Mercury and shaped its current composition. Additional high-resolution images and altimetry of the surface could be used to further analyze Mercury's crater population, particularly to understand better the prominent role of secondary cratering on Mercury in comparison with the Moon.

c) Polar deposits

The polar ice deposits in the permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) of Mercury are the closest analog to the lunar PSR ice deposits. They provide a natural laboratory for studying the retention, modification, and loss of volatiles on airless bodies (Chabot et al., 2014a; Deutsch et al., 2016). It is noteworthy that **there appears to be much more ice in Mercury's PSRs than in the lunar PSRs** (Lawrence, 2017). Understanding the origin of Mercury's PSR ice deposits provides key information on volatile delivery to the inner solar system. Better understanding the difference between the ice deposits of the Moon and Mercury would improve understanding of potential lunar resources and could help to inform future lunar human/robotic exploration.

To advance understanding of Mercury's polar deposits, orbital missions should map the distribution of the PSR ice using visible (e.g. the ShadowCam instrument on the KPLO lunar mission) and IR spectrometers, as well as radar and lidar. Radar studies can also be conducted from Earth-based telescopes (Slade et al., 1992). Landed missions should measure the chemical composition and stratigraphy of the deposits using onboard instrumentation ideally in concert with rovers that can analyze these deposits in detail. Ultimately, a sample return mission would be needed for a full characterization of the cryogenic record on Mercury. The compositions could be compared with the chemical composition of cometary materials, asteroids and meteorites, Kuiper belt objects, and ices on Ceres and outer solar system satellites, thereby providing insight into the origin of inner solar system volatiles.

d) Exospheric and magnetospheric processes

The study at Mercury of space weathering, exospheric generation, and magnetospheric dynamics has a broad impact on the study of other solar and extrasolar airless bodies. With an intrinsic planetary field that is about 1% that of the Earth, Mercury cannot stand-off the solar wind with the same effectiveness. This creates a much smaller magnetosphere, with boundaries that are much closer to the surface of the planet, especially the dayside (Winslow et al., 2013). The dynamics of the magnetosphere appear very different at Mercury compared to the Earth. For instance, on Earth, incoming/outgoing field-aligned (Birkeland) currents close in the ionosphere, whereas at Mercury, field-aligned electric currents close below the surface because of the absence of a (significant) ionosphere and flow radially in

the upper crust and laterally at depth (e.g., Anderson et al., 2018; Shi et al., 2025). Solar wind pressure, on average 10 times higher than at Earth, and magnetic reconnection on the dayside magnetopause act to further reduce this distance, including cases where the entire dayside is subject to direct bombardment by the solar wind plasma (Slavin et al., 2014; 2019; Jia et al., 2019; Winslow et al., 2020). This combination results in **a very active environment for space weathering through plasma precipitation** (Kallio and Janhunen, 2003; Winslow et al., 2014; Fatemi et al., 2020; Raines et al., 2022; Lavorenti et al., 2023a 2023b) **and, at times, significant variability in Mercury’s exosphere** (Mangano et al., 2015; Orsini et al., 2018; Milillo et al., 2021).

Knowledge gained at Mercury in the two areas discussed above can be broadly applied to other airless bodies, such as the Moon or asteroids, or those where the solar wind interaction may be almost unknown, such as exoplanets. Compared with the Earth, Mercury experiences much-more frequent magnetic reconnection on its dayside magnetopause, largely because it occurs over a broader range of interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) directions (Slavin et al., 2009; DiBraccio et al., 2013; Gershman et al., 2013). It also has a radically different time scale for plasma and magnetic field convection through the magnetosphere—two to three minutes, on average, as compared to 60 minutes at Earth (Slavin et al., 2010; 2014; 2019). This puts Mercury’s magnetosphere, while principally Earth-like, into a distinctly different region of parameter space. **Mercury is an excellent place to test our understanding of the drivers and responses of Earth’s magnetosphere, as well as those of the very different magnetospheres of the outer planets.**

e) Core structure and evolution

Mercury hosts the largest core by mass fraction among the terrestrial planets. Due to the relative proximity of its core to the surface, **Mercury presents a unique opportunity to understand in detail how metallic cores evolve and are layered.** Indeed, characterizing Mercury’s core properties is essential for determining the overall composition and evolution of the innermost planet. Current understanding of the properties of Mercury’s core rests on 1) MESSENGER-based determinations of the rotational state (i.e., amplitude of the physical libration and the orientation of the planet), 2) the second-degree harmonics of the gravity field (e.g., Margot et al 2018, Bertone et al., 2021) and 3) and laboratory measurements of the physical properties (e.g., Pommier et al., 2019). New data on the state, density, and composition of the core are expected from the BepiColombo mission (Genova et al., 2021).

Several measurements could provide additional insights into Mercury’s core, as follows. Constraining the rotation state and orientation (i.e., via tracking surface features and tracking the gravity field of the whole planet, including understanding differences between the approaches in current data) remains a major opportunity for elucidating the interior structure and composition (via constraining density variations). Electromagnetic approaches (e.g., focusing on currents and induced magnetic fields in the interior, or studying the spatial structure of the core magnetic field) provide critical independent ways to determine the depth to the core and the conductivity structure of the mantle (e.g., Johnson et al., 2016, Wardinski et al., 2021). Measurements of the substantial solid body tides and density structure (e.g., via k₂, k₂ phase, h₂) on Mercury would present a unique

opportunity to constrain the properties of the mantle and core (e.g., Steinbrügge et al. 2018). Seismic observations of Mercury would present the opportunity to independently and precisely determine properties for the size and seismic velocities of the core necessary for strongly constraining the size, composition, and layering of the liquid and potentially solid layers of Mercury’s core. New constraints about crust and mantle compositions would improve the ability to resolve core properties (e.g., Lark et al. 2022). Laboratory and computational measurements for materials at Mercury conditions (e.g., equations of state, melting curves, rheological properties) are also needed for interpretation of future Mercury seismic data.

1.3 Inform our understanding of rocky exoplanets

a) Mercury as an exoplanet

Mercury formed under much more reducing conditions than any of the other terrestrial planets (Zolotov et al., 2013; Ebel and Stewart, 2018). The low oxygen fugacity (fO_2) exerted a primary control on Mercury’s chemical and physical properties, and set it on a strongly divergent evolutionary path compared with the other terrestrial planets (Boukaré et al., 2019). In particular, Mercury’s S-rich and Fe-depleted crust and mantle is directly due to its low fO_2 (Nittler et al., 2011; McCubbin, et al., 2012; Namur et al., 2016a,b), but it is not understood why Mercury is so much more reducing than the other planets. One explanation is that the very inner solar system was enriched in C, which formed CO, lowering oxygen partial pressure (Ebel and Stewart, 2018). Many observed rocky exoplanets are as close, or closer, to their host star as Mercury, and many orbit stars with higher C/O ratios than our Sun. Thus, many currently detected exoplanets should be Mercury-like, highly-reduced sulfide-rich planets (Bond et al., 2010). **Understanding the role that low fO_2 had in Mercury’s evolution, including its high density and high volatile content, is key to understanding highly reduced exoplanets.** Likewise, observations of the distribution of high-density, inner planets in extrasolar systems should shed light on possible formation mechanisms for Mercury.

The identification of additional so-called super-Mercuries (e.g., Rodriguez et al. 2022) in known multi-planet systems, with next generation telescopes like the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST), will also be useful for uncovering the processes involved in Mercury’s accretion. If most planetary systems’ bulk density distributions are hierarchical, it would strengthen the argument that Mercury formed in an inner, Fe-rich region of the Sun’s natal protoplanetary disk (Johansen and Dorn, 2022). In contrast, if Fe-rich planets prove to be common in all types of systems, it would be reasonable to assume that Mercury is the one planet in the solar system which has had much of its mantle stripped away. Improved telescopic observations of exoplanet densities and orbits would further our understanding of possible Mercury formation scenarios.

b) Exoplanet exospheres and magnetospheres

For those exoplanets that have exospheres instead of collisional atmospheres, spectroscopic telescope studies can reveal details of the planet’s surface. In these cases, the measured spectra can be strongly

affected by space weathering. **With its close proximity to the Sun, highly active magnetosphere, and non-collisional atmosphere to shield it, Mercury is an excellent laboratory for the study of space weathering** (Domingue et al. 2007; 2014).

A lot has been learned about Mercury's magnetospheric convection patterns and its drivers, informed by MESSENGER orbital data and global numerical modeling (Slavin et al., 2018). Patterns of solar wind precipitation on the surface of Mercury have been estimated, and work has begun to compare these with visible light measurements of the surface to make the connection to this aspect of space weathering (e.g. Gershman et al., 2015a; Fatemi et al., 2020; Raines et al., 2022; Lavorenti et al., 2023a, 2023b). Understanding of all these processes will be greatly improved by measurements from BepiColombo, with the combination of its Mercury Planetary Orbiter (MPO), in a low-altitude, nearly circular orbit, and Mio (Mercury Magnetospheric Orbiter), often acting as either an upstream solar wind or down-magnetotail magnetospheric convection monitor (Benkhoff et al., 2021). **Based on our understanding of Mercury, it might be possible to use visible light measurements of an exoplanet to understand aspects of its solar wind interaction and even infer the existence of an intrinsic magnetic field.**

2. Understand the origins of Mercury, from accretion to solidification

2.1 Investigate compositional building blocks

a) Understanding meteoritic contributions

Understanding the materials that went into building Mercury is key for understanding its composition, evolution, and current state. Although no samples (i.e., meteorites) from Mercury have so far been identified, the similar low fO_2 of enstatite chondrites, aubrites, and other reduced meteorite classes makes them useful analogs of the building blocks of Mercury (Wasson, 1988; McCoy et al., 1999; Taylor and Scott, 2003; Brown and Elkins-Tanton, 2009; Malavergne et al., 2010; Nittler et al., 2011; Udry et al., 2019; Wilbur et al., 2022; Hammouda et al., 2022). Much of what we understand about Mercury's composition and internal structure is based upon studies of these reduced meteorites, in addition to the geochemical data from MESSENGER. **Further work to analyze the major, trace, and isotopic compositions of highly reduced meteorite classes will be invaluable in understanding how Mercury was formed.**

Experimental and numerical studies of reduced meteorite phase equilibria, and formation from the solar nebula, will provide models for how Mercury's building blocks could have formed and aggregated. Improved chronological studies of the reduced meteorites would shed light on the sequence and rates of early solar system processes that may have formed Mercury. There should be a concerted effort to identify possible mercurian meteorites in existing collections (Tissot et al., 2023). Improved compositional and mineralogic data from orbital and landed missions, as well as Earth-based observations, will help to define the building blocks of Mercury, but **ultimately, what will be needed to answer these questions is a returned sample from the surface of Mercury, so that state-of-the-art elemental and isotopic analyses can be conducted on Earth** (Mezger et al., 2020).

b) Origin and retention of volatiles during formation

To explain many of Mercury's unusual features, including its high bulk-Fe content, many models invoke a high-temperature formation for the planet, and therefore predict a volatile-depleted composition. MESSENGER results demonstrated, however, that Mercury appears not to be volatile depleted. For example, its K/Th ratio (volatile element/non-volatile element) is the same as that of Earth and Mars. In addition, Mercury's surface is rich in S, Na, and Cl, and pyroclastic deposits (driven by volatiles) abound. How Mercury retained its volatiles while forming so close to the Sun is not understood. It may be due to changing geochemical behavior under reducing conditions where nominally lithophile elements become more chalcophile and siderophile (McCubbin et al. 2012; Wohlers and Wood 2015; Boujibar et al. 2019; Pirotte et al. 2023; McCubbin and Anzures 2025). Reduced enstatite chondrites are also enriched in moderately volatile lithophiles such as Na and K (Fogel et al. 1989; Keil 2010; Weisberg and Kimura 2012; Wilbur et al. 2022; Hammouda et al. 2022). **Better analysis of moderately volatile elements on Mercury's surface, as well as more detailed studies of volatiles in reduced meteorites, will provide insight into how the innermost planet retained its volatile-rich surface.**

The speciation of volatile elements during Mercury's formation would have depended on conditions in the early hot inner disk. Modeling and experiments on volatile partitioning and speciation at relevant conditions would help to determine their chalcophile/lithophile character and how refractory their host solids are as a function of fO_2 . Preliminary calculations indicate that at least some elements (S, Cl, K) become more refractory in solar-system vapor enriched in carbon (low fO_2) (Ebel and Sack, 2013). **A landed mission with the ability to analyze volatile element concentrations in-situ would provide invaluable insight into the building blocks of Mercury.** Additionally, a sample return mission would allow detailed isotopic analysis of volatile elements as well as analysis of volatiles in polycrystalline material.

c) Constraints on bulk composition from surface chemistry

As with all of the terrestrial planets, the bulk composition of Mercury must be inferred from a combination of geophysical measurements (some of which can sample to the center of the planet), geochemical measurements (which are restricted to the surface), and laboratory experiments at relevant pressure and temperature (P, T) values and compositions (Nittler et al., 2018; Cartier and Wood, 2019). Geologic processes, including cratering and faulting, can exhume material from depth, allowing direct analysis of interior materials. However, much of our understanding of the interior composition of planets, including their overall bulk composition, comes from the analysis of erupted lavas combined with understanding of melting processes through experiments and thermodynamic modeling (Charlier et al., 2013; Namur et al., 2013, 2016a; Boujibar et al., 2014, 2025). Thus, **improved analysis of the composition of Mercury's surface, in both spatial resolution and accuracy of geochemical and mineralogical measurements, will directly lead to improved constraints on the compositional structure of the planet's interior.**

Landed missions with the capability to analyze major and trace element composition, mineralogy, and isotopic composition, would provide a huge leap forward in our understanding of Mercury's surface

chemistry. Key targets might be areas where material from depth is exhumed by impact craters and areas where lava flows with a range of compositions could be accessed with a rover. Mercury's high-magnesium region (HMR) could also be a key target for a landed mission as it may represent part of the mantle exhumed by an early, large, impact or an area covered by highly-magnesian (and sulfur-rich) lavas (Weider et al., 2015). Landed missions would also provide critical 'ground truth' for remotely sensed compositional and mineralogical datasets.

High-pressure experiments will also be key to interpreting the surface compositional and mineralogical variations, but to date, relatively few experiments have been conducted under Mercury-relevant conditions. Experiments exploring a wider range of compositions, fO_2 , and volatile contents are thus required. As the magmas undoubtedly underwent cooling and fractionation as they migrated from the mantle to the surface, models of how mercurian magmas would differentiate are also needed. A range of mantle compositions, magma ocean solidification scenarios, and melting models should be explored through a combination of experiments, thermodynamic modeling, and physical modeling of melting processes.

2.2 Explore formation scenarios

a) Dynamics of early accretion of materials (dust to planetesimals)

Understanding the dynamics of accretion—from dust, to planetesimals, to planets—is critical to constraining the building blocks of Mercury. Most dynamical collision models predict Mercury should have a substantially larger mass and a less inclined/eccentric orbit (Nesvorny et al., 2021; Woo et al., 2022; Clement et al., 2023). The mass deficit and orbit are explained by post-formation stripping of mass by one or more large collisions or by the inward migration of Mercury from farther out in the disk. Each of these models has implications for the composition of Mercury, the timing of its formation, and the size of the other terrestrial planets. Improved dynamical models are thus needed that explore longer periods of early solar system evolution, more realistic collision physics, and the effects of mass-depleted zones within the disk.

b) Origin scenarios (planetesimal collisions, orbit migration and large core/mantle ratio)

Mercury's large core, diminutive mass, and dynamically isolated orbit are rarely reproduced in terrestrial accretion models (Chambers, 2001; Clement et al., 2023; Lykawka and Ito, 2023) and have long been interpreted to imply a unique formation history (Morgan and Anders, 1980; Chapman, 1988). Mercury's mysterious origin is even more enigmatic when viewed within the context of numerous exoplanet systems; as many as 50% of Sun-like stars possess >Earth-mass planets with orbital periods much less than ~100 days (Howard et al., 2012; Petigura et al., 2018). In light of MESSENGER's findings, two broad classes of models aiming to explain Mercury's large core mass fraction remain viable. In the first, the mantle of a primordially larger Mercury is stripped in one or more violent collisions with another proto-planet (a "chaotic" origin: Benz et al., 2007; Asphaug and Reufer, 2014). However, in such an event, Mercury would likely re-accrete substantial amounts of the lost material (Gladman and Coffey, 2009). Moreover, such an event would require improbably large impact velocities (Jackson et al., 2018).

In the alternative class of models, Mercury forms within a reservoir of objects with Fe/Si ratios that are boosted as a result of a process that differentially affected the infant Sun's protoplanetary disk (an "orderly" origin: Ebel and Alexander, 2011; Wurm et al., 2013; Kruss and Wurm, 2018; Johansen and Dorn, 2022). However, it remains difficult to envision how this process only affected Mercury because of the high degree of mixing known to occur during the epoch of terrestrial planet formation (Raymond et al., 2006; Woo et al., 2022).

An "orderly" origin for Mercury axiomatically implies that it formed much closer to the Sun, within a different reservoir of material than Earth and Venus. In contrast, the most likely impact scenario would be one where Mercury originated in the vicinity of Earth and Venus, and was scattered out of the region after its core mass fraction was altered (Clement et al., 2019; Franco et al., 2022; Izidoro et al., 2022). **Thus, improved constraints on the age of Mercury's surface and its bulk and isotopic compositions from high-resolution surface images, in-situ lander measurements, and/or age-dating of returned samples of the oldest crust could break degeneracies between these models.** It is also possible that an as-yet unidentified mercurian meteorite currently exists in our collection. Indeed, there are undifferentiated meteorites with similarly low fO_2 whose origins remain murky (Ebel and Alexander, 2011; Weisberg and Kimura, 2012), and in-situ elemental and isotopic measurements could be used to establish such a link.

c) Volatile record (before and after gas loss from the inner disk)

Mercury is surprisingly volatile-rich both in its interior (Peplowski et al., 2012). The interior composition indicates that Mercury retained volatiles throughout its formation and solidification, despite its proximity to the Sun. Experiments on volatile solubility in mantle and core phases are needed, as well as physical models of magma ocean differentiation, to constrain how Mercury could have retained its volatiles. Analysis of samples on the surface would constrain how much of Mercury's volatile inventory was lost, as well as their distribution in the interior, both in the silicate and metallic portions of the planet. Improved models of the early evolution of Mercury's magnetic field are also needed to constrain the extent to which it could have shielded Mercury from volatile stripping by the Sun (Johnson et al., 2015).

2.3 Understand global differentiation/evolution

a) Initial differentiation (core and mantle)

Models for the formation of Mercury's core are strongly linked to the formation of Mercury itself. If Mercury formed directly from metal-rich building blocks, then there was little mantle for the core-forming metal to react with, possibly promoting a mantle and core that are not in chemical equilibrium with each other. Whereas if Mercury were larger, then core-formation processes may have been similar to those hypothesized for Earth, where the traverse of metal through a sizable mantle induced equilibrium, at least at the start (Trønnes et al., 2019).

Traces of Mercury's initial differentiation should be recorded in the composition of Mercury's mantle (and lavas), in their trace elements and isotopic compositions, including for the

siderophile elements, as well as W, Si, and Fe isotopes (Righter, 2003; Helfrich et al., 2019). Measurements either in situ or on returned samples would thus provide valuable insights into core formation on Mercury. Experimental studies to constrain partitioning of heat-producing elements between mantle and core analogs at pressure and temperature conditions relevant to Mercury are needed to interpret the geochemical observations and provide valuable insights into core formation (Boujibar et al., 2019; Pirotte et al., 2023). Geophysical constraints on the size of the core and putative inner core, as well as the core density also inform formation models, because they help constrain the concentrations of the light elements in the core (e.g. S, Si, C) and heat loss. Improved geodynamic models are needed to understand the potential effects of Mercury's thin mantle on core segregation. These should include the effects of low fO_2 on the physical properties of silicate melts (Anzures et al., 2020; Mouser et al., 2021; Pommier et al., 2023) and metallic melts (e.g., Pommier et al., 2019; Berrada et al., 2022).

b) Solidification of the magma ocean and production of a primary crust

The solidification of Mercury's magma ocean established its initial internal structure and set the stage for its subsequent evolution. Due to the high-S and low-Fe solubility in the magma ocean, and the presence of C, the solidification and differentiation of Mercury's magma ocean is very different from that of the Moon (Boukaré et al., 2019). Constraining what phases formed from Mercury's magma ocean, as well as their chemical and physical properties (Anzures et al., 2020; Mouser et al., 2021; Pommier et al., 2023), is key to addressing several questions about Mercury's early evolution, including: Did graphite and/or Ca-Mg sulfide float to form a primary crust (Vander Kaaden and McCubbin, 2015)? Are sulfides abundant in the mantle (Lark et al., 2022)? Was there enough density increase during fractionation to drive subsequent overturn, as suggested for the Moon (Mouser and Dygert, 2023)? Did the initial layering produced by magma ocean solidification survive to produce the variety of magmas seen on Mercury's surface, or was it homogenized by convection (Charlier et al., 2013)?

Experiments under Mercury-relevant conditions are needed to constrain how Mercury's magma ocean differentiated. Critical measurements include phase compositions as well as their physical properties (e.g., density, electrical and thermal conductivity, viscosity, surface energy), where it is critical to understand the behavior of silicate magmas under highly reducing conditions. Models of crystal/melt separation in the magma ocean are needed to define layering and melt retention in the mantle. Geophysical measurements (e.g., gravity, topography, shape, and heat flow) can constrain current mantle density and structure, which may help to inform magma ocean models. New measurements of lava composition of lavas (major/trace elements and isotopic) and diversity would greatly increase our understanding of how the magma ocean formed and crystallized.

c) Core structure and dynamics during magma ocean solidification

Once Mercury's core formed, subsequent cooling was controlled by heat loss through the core–mantle boundary (CMB) and internal heat production. As the magma ocean cooled and solidified, the core would have responded to the changing boundary conditions, which would have affected the thermal gradient and the possible formation of a sulfide-rich layer at the CMB (Smith et al., 2012). Such a layer

might have incorporated some amount of radioactive heat-producing elements (U, Th, K) in the sulfides (Boukaré et al., 2019; Pirotte et al., 2023). However, cooling models of the planet showed that this FeS layer should have negligible effects on core dynamics and the magnetic field (Davies et al., 2024).

Future observations from BepiColombo will help to improve our existing models of core convection, and further our understanding of the very early stages of Mercury's core. Better characterization of the timing and extent of planet contraction may constrain the earliest core history. The discovery of a crustal magnetic field spatially associated with Caloris Planitia may indicate magnetic remanence acquired during the Caloris impact (3.8 to 3.9 Ga) and that the core field was active early in Mercury's history (Johnson et al., 2015). Combined geochronologic and paleomagnetic analysis of minerals (e.g., zircon) or rock fragments in regolith, either in situ or in a returned sample, could constrain the early evolution of the core. Studies of remnant magnetism in the crust and determination of its geological context could further elucidate the history of Mercury's dynamo.

3. Characterize Mercury's evolution since solidification

3.1 Study past geological processes

a) Cratering record

A true understanding of Mercury's impact flux through time, which forms the basis for Mercury's chronology (Spudis and Guest, 1988), requires measuring the absolute age from a known geological terrain on Mercury via in situ age dating or sample return. In the absence of such measurements, our understanding is extrapolated from the Moon, compensating for Mercury's distinct gravity and impact velocity. Observed primary crater size frequency distributions (CSFDs) are translated into a production function and absolute chronology through assumed models of impact flux and crater scaling relationships (e.g., Spudis and Guest, 1998; Marchi et al., 2009; Le Feuvre and Wieczorek, 2011). The timing of geological events, including stratigraphic markers like Tolstoj and Caloris, can be significantly affected by what models are used (e.g., Denevi et al., 2018). Further, secondary craters may contaminate the CSFDs for diameters <10 km (Bierhaus et al., 2018). Thus, crater-based dating of the youngest or smallest units and understanding of the primary impact flux that relies on these small crater sizes requires an understanding of secondary crater production and distribution.

To improve knowledge of Mercury's impact flux through time, one aim is to study the characteristics and dynamics of small-body populations in the solar system, to understand the sources of the impactors. Further research on lunar and martian chronology, along with theoretical studies of the evolution of small-body populations in the solar system, could narrow the uncertainties concerning Mercury's geological evolution. Detailed searches, especially by spacecraft orbiting near Mercury, for small body populations interior to Mercury's orbit would determine the potential role of such impactors in affecting the changing rate of crater formation on the planet. Geophysical and geochemical

studies could shed light on the effect that basin-forming impacts have on modifying the geological and geochemical characteristics of the surface.

Another aim is to better characterize primary crater-size frequency distributions and the contribution of secondary craters to the cratering record. By investigating the morphology of small impact craters and the variations in post-formation modification processes, we may better understand the differences in the secondary crater distribution on Mercury compared with other bodies such as the Moon. Additionally, the spatial variation of crater modification will elucidate the processes that have shaped different parts of the surface. High-resolution orbital images and digital terrain models over a larger percentage of the surface, such as will be acquired from SIMBIO-SYS on the BepiColombo mission (Da Deppo et al., 2017; Cremonese et al., 2020), will allow detailed characterization of crater morphology and improve the ability to identify secondary craters.

To improve Mercury-specific crater scaling models, an aim is to better understand the compositional and physical attributes of the surface (strength, bulk density, porosity, layering) and how they change laterally across the surface and as a function of depth (e.g., Genova et al., 2021). Orbital spectroscopic observations and in situ sample analysis would improve our understanding of the composition of the surface and its inferred mechanical properties. Experimental and numerical impact studies would also improve models for how target properties, higher projectile velocities, and higher target temperatures might affect crater size.

b) Timing and styles of volcanism

An aim is to better understand the composition, volatile content, and speciation that drove the vesiculation, eruption, and timing of volcanic deposits across Mercury. Volcanic deposits on Mercury are generally characterized as either smooth plains or explosive/pyroclastic deposits. Smooth plains occupy about a quarter of the planet's surface. The vast majority by volume of these units were emplaced as effusive volcanic products by ~3.5 billion years ago. Subsequently, global contraction appears to have suppressed large effusive volcanic episodes (Byrne et al., 2016). Some deposits have morphological and spectral characteristics of lavas, whereas others may be ponded impact melt (Denevi et al., 2013). Many smooth plains units are collocated with impact features, suggestive of a causal relationship (Byrne et al., 2018b) that needs to be further investigated. Other aims are to identify if the spectral characteristics of smooth plains have systematic temporal or spatial variations, and eruption rates and compositions.

Pyroclastic deposits have been found to be long-lived, with some of them less than 1 billion years old (Thomas et al., 2014b), but there is an intriguing paucity of constructional volcanic features such as shield or cone-like volcanoes (Wright et al., 2018). **Determining the timing, rate, and volatile speciation of explosive volcanic eruptions and how they continued after the cessation of major effusive activity and the onset of global contraction is an important aim.** Carbon and sulfur in such deposits are depleted relative to Mercury's surface (Weider et al., 2016), which has been interpreted as indicating that C and S were the driving volatile species, but the key species that drove the explosive volcanism still remain to be confirmed (Iacovino et al., 2023).

To achieve these aims, high-resolution images and spectral data, together with detailed mapping of unit superposition and onlap relations and improved crater production models for Mercury, are required—some of which will be provided by BepiColombo (Cremonese et al., 2020; Bunce et al., 2020; Hiesinger et al., 2020). Moreover, more experiments are needed to constrain the solubility of volatiles in magmas at relevant compositions and fO_2 and what gas species magmas would emit as they erupt. New thermodynamic models of low- fO_2 and high-sulfur-fugacity (fS) conditions will need to be developed. Ultimately in situ geochemical and geochronological analysis of smooth plains, or returned samples from these regions and/or sites of explosive volcanism would answer open questions related to these aims.

c) Timing and styles of tectonics

Mercury has undergone global contraction since at least the Calorian era, evinced by the global distribution of crustal shortening features (Byrne et al., 2018a) and superposition relationships with craters of various degradation stages (Crane and Klimczak, 2017). Tectonic activity prior to that phase of global shortening, however, is not well understood. Mercury was likely much more active—volcanically, tectonically, and otherwise—early in its geologic history. **It is therefore an aim to identify, describe, and model the oldest preserved (thrust) faults on the body to understand their structural style and subsurface geometry, timing, and locations.** It is also an aim to understand the topographic expressions of thrusts, their tectonic patterns, and their relationship to other long-wavelength variations in the lithosphere. This is important for constraining the total tectonic history with individual contributions from contraction, changes in rotation, vertical loads on the lithosphere, and the spatial pattern of variations in thickness and strength of the crust and lithosphere. To achieve this aim, high-resolution topography measurements with global coverage are needed, as well as detailed estimates of the timing of faulting. Furthermore, model-derived geologically reasonable interpretations of subsurface geometries of thrust faults are needed to constrain estimates of Mercury's radial contraction. These geologically reasonable subsurface geometries might also illuminate the physical properties of Mercury's rocks and its crustal structure. It will be important to validate the model solutions of subsurface geometries at appropriate Earth analogue sites.

Extensional deformation on Mercury is much more spatially restricted than shortening and is mostly found in volcanically flooded impact basins (Freed et al., 2012) associated with slumps on crater walls, or along the fold axes of major shortening structures (Man et al., 2023). However, Mercury may have undergone an early phase of planetary expansion leading to rifting and giant dike formation, similar to what is found on the Moon (Andrews-Hanna et al., 2013). To address this topic, high-resolution gravity field measurements, comparable to that returned by the GRAIL mission, are required to detect linear gravity anomalies associated with ancient rifts or dikes. Further, only limited instances of strike-slip deformation have been reported on Mercury (e.g., Galluzzi et al., 2015). High-resolution images and topographic datasets are required to determine if this kind of deformation is more widespread and to elucidate the nature of ancient tectonic activity global.

d) Relationships between volcanism, tectonism, volatiles

Connecting volcanism and tectonism on Mercury is key to understanding the formation and spatial distribution of volcanic vents, the emplacement of the smooth plains materials, and the connection between intrusive and extrusive igneous processes. Since fractures in fumarole systems serve as conduits for gases (Munaretto et al., 2023), it is important to understand the interplay of fracture systems and fumarolic activities for Mercury-relevant conditions. To achieve that, it is essential to conduct field work at analog sites on Earth at permafrost terrains or sulfur-rich volcanic crater formations like solfataras and their connection to fractures (Phillips et al., 2021). To connect intrusive and extrusive volcanism, analysis of upcoming data from the Mercury Orbiter Radio Science Experiment (MORE) (less et al., 2021) and geologic mapping using SIMBIO-SYS (Cremonese et al., 2020) on BepiColombo will be needed. Gravity anomaly mapping can be used to: detect intrusive bodies; determine the location, orientation, and characteristics of volcanic conduits that produced the smooth plains; more tightly constrain models of crustal thickness; and address why smooth plains are concentrated in the northern hemisphere. Improved spectral and spatial observations from orbiters, together with in-situ sampling of Mercury's crust, will ultimately constrain the compositional variations between the explosive and effusive volcanic units, determine the volatiles driving volcanism, and further elucidate the relationship between tectonics and volcanism.

e) Long-wavelength topography

MESSENGER-derived topography of Mercury's northern hemisphere reveals broad regions of undulating relief, which appear to be genetically independent of other, major topographic modifications such as faulting, cratering, and volcanism. These variations occur at a range of scales from the degree 2 shape of the planet (Phillips et al., 2018) to the undulatory patterns in the Caloris basin or broad, isolated rises, the most prominent of which is seen in Borealis Planitia (the Northern Rise) (Zuber et al., 2012; Klimczak et al., 2013). The superposition relationships of geologic features indicate that long-wavelength topographic changes occurred subsequent to the craters and volcanically resurfaced areas that they affect. There is minimal correlation between gravity and topography, suggesting that the observed topography is supported by multiple processes. Modeling indicates that folding is unlikely to have been produced by global contraction (Kay and Dombard, 2019). Such processes may include top loading of an elastic lithosphere, bottom loading, crustal thickening, and/or dynamic topography. It is an aim to elucidate how, where, and when each of these processes operated. Because of Mercury's thin mantle, processes at the core-mantle boundary (CMB) may have an observable effect on long-wavelength topography. Thus, it is an aim to characterize how plausible different CMB processes are and how they affect the long-wavelength topography. To achieve these aims, some improvements in observations on topography and gravity from BepiColombo, especially for the southern hemisphere, and ultimately major such improvements by a mission similar in design to GRAIL, will provide further insight into the distribution of the long wavelength undulations. Their causes must be further studied by modeling plausible CMB processes and their expressions in gravity, topography and the magnetic field (Plattner and Johnson, 2021).

f) Structure of the crust and lithosphere

Characterizing the structure of the crust and lithosphere, and their relationship to geologic features and surface compositions, is vital to understanding how the planet's crust formed and the endogenic and exogenic processes that have shaped the surface. MESSENGER provided a first look at the topography, crustal thickness, and crustal density over Mercury's northern hemisphere (e.g., James et al., 2015; Padovan et al., 2015; Sori, 2018; Beuthe et al., 2020.). Improved characterization of enigmatic features of the lithosphere, such as long-wavelength topographic variations, will provide new insights into mantle structure and thermal state. Constraining lithospheric thickness through time is important to put observed surface features in context and to estimate how interior heat has declined with time. Like the Moon, Mercury's shape and gravity figure are not in hydrostatic equilibrium. The reason for this is yet unexplained but is important for formation and early evolution scenarios. Global high-resolution gravity and topography data are important for revealing the support mechanisms for major features such as the Northern Rise and the Caloris basin, the history of heat flow, and the origin of the global, non-hydrostatic shape of the planet.

g) Heat flow

The loss of heat through the surface of a planet is a crucial window into the current and historical operation of the planet's interior. **Understanding how Mercury has lost heat is directly related to the composition of the planet, its tectonic and volcanic activity, and how the magnetic field is generated.** The primary long-term source of heat in Mercury is the decay of radioactive elements in the interior (e.g., Hauck et al., 2004). Constraining the distribution of heat-producing elements across and below the surface is therefore essential for understanding how the interior has evolved. This could be accomplished through improved measurement of heat producing elements at a variety of scales across the surface, determination of surface rock and mineral compositions that host heat-producing elements, determination of partitioning relationships for heat-producing elements in Mercury analog materials, and identification and compositional analysis of any Mercury meteorites.

Determining variations in lithospheric thickness at a variety of scales (e.g., through studies of lithospheric deformation at faults, characterization of high-resolution gravity and topography data, determination of the depth of seismogenic activity) can also place constraints on past heat flow from the mantle (e.g., Grott et al., 2011; Byrne et al., 2014). In addition, estimating the thermal structure of the shallow subsurface (e.g., via direct measurement with heat flow probes on a landed mission, high resolution thermal mapping, estimation of surficial porosity via high-resolution gravity measurements, and modeling based on surface properties, etc.) is critical for constraining modern heat flow, tectonic activity, and the sequestration and liberation of volatiles.

h) Regolith formation and mixing

Understanding of Mercury's regolith can benefit from our knowledge of the Moon's regolith, but there are significant differences in meteoroid, micrometeoroid, and proton fluxes, surface composition, and daytime temperature between the two bodies. By characterizing the differences in regolith production at Mercury in comparison to the Moon, we may better understand the

environmental and compositional factors that influence regolith development on airless bodies in general. In situ analyses of Mercury regolith from a landed investigation (akin to information gleaned from returned Apollo drill cores) would inform understanding of the rate of impact gardening and the depth to which processes affect the regolith. Regolith formation and mixing models can be improved by understanding the mass, velocity, and flux of the meteoroid population near Mercury. Regolith models can also be improved through observations of degrading features (e.g., depth-diameter ratio and the shape of ejecta blankets around fresh craters on Mercury) and models of topographic diffusion such as those conducted for the Moon (Fassett and Thomson, 2014; Fassett et al., 2017). Such studies are most robust when remote sensing techniques covering several depth scales are used together (e.g., radar observations on the decameter scale and visible light on the surface). It is also necessary to understand the mechanical properties of Mercury's regolith and how it may differ from other airless bodies. Remote thermal infrared radiometry (e.g., from MERTIS on BepiColombo; Hiesinger et al., 2010; 2020) will allow analysis of thermophysical properties. Future landed images of regolith grains could be used to investigate particle size, strength, cohesion, and porosity.

Space weathering at Mercury is thought to be dominated by the formation of agglutinitic deposits through micrometeorite bombardment and to be lacking in solar wind ion sputtering (Hapke, 2001). Additionally, Mercury's extreme temperature range has implications for the diffusion in glass and crystal growth processes in the regolith (Noble and Pieters, 2003). These properties have important effects on the spectral properties of the soil. Photometric modeling has found that Mercury's regolith is likely smoother at micrometer scales and has a smaller mean particle size distribution compared with lunar regolith, which is consistent with a larger flux and higher velocity of impactors than at the Moon (Domingue et al., 2016). The intense space weathering environment may have resulted in a higher abundance of agglutinates, leading to smoother grains thereby reducing surface roughness. While Mercury's deficient 1-micron band could be due to a lack of iron, it is plausible that the lack of a 1-micron band is the result of an amorphous surface rich in agglutinates (McClintock et al., 2008; Robinson et al., 2008). Color imaging and analysis before and after a physical interaction with the regolith (e.g., with a lander arm) would help to elucidate the effects of space weathering on Mercury's regolith as well as regolith depth. Characterizing regolith optical maturation rates on Mercury (and on airless bodies in general) is essential to interpreting multispectral reflectance measurements (Braden et al., 2013).

3.2 Understand processes behind the chemical and mineralogical diversity of the crust

a) Geochemical variations

Data from MESSENGER's geochemical instruments revealed the presence of geochemical terranes in Mercury's northern hemisphere—regions with geographically distinct compositions (e.g., McCoy et al., 2018; Peplowski and Stockstill-Cahill, 2019) that are thought to be primarily igneous in origin. Several petrologic studies have been conducted to ascertain the conditions that produced the geochemical terranes (Charlier et al., 2013; Cartier et al., 2014; Namur et al., 2016a, Vander Kaaden et al., 2016; Boujibar et al., 2025), but **further progress in understanding Mercury's geochemical diversity requires improvements in the experimental (melting/crystallization) data available for diverse,**

Mercury-relevant (i.e., highly reduced) magma compositions and in the techniques used to model geologic processes on Mercury.

There are still several remaining questions about the terranes. For example, can they be produced from a single mantle composition, or do they require substantially different sources? Did the melting style change over time as the planet cooled and the lithosphere thickened? How did the compressional state of the lithosphere affect how magmas ascended to the surface? Given the relatively large size of the core, and its proximity to the surface, did the core exert more direct control on magmatism than other planets? Answering these questions requires experiments that explore the evolution of both core and mantle, as well as modeling of the dynamics and melting of the mantle. Improved compositional and mineralogical data from spacecraft are key to answering these questions. BepiColombo's geochemical and mineralogical instruments will provide spatially resolved geochemical data for Mercury's southern hemisphere that can be used to determine if additional geochemical terranes are present. Landed spacecraft, equipped with instruments to study the elemental, isotopic, and mineralogical compositions of the crust could provide such local-scale information, but would also provide critically important ground-truth data for the remote data sets already obtained (Ernst et al., 2022). Investigating Mercury's geochemical diversity in the context of other terrestrial bodies will also provide important insights.

b) Variations in mineralogy

One of the largest existing knowledge gaps for Mercury is the mineralogy of the surface. Due to the low fO_2 , the silicate minerals and melts have little FeO content, and so have no spectral features in the VNIR range of MESSENGER's MASCS spectrometer and MDIS multispectral camera (Izenberg et al., 2014). To date, no minerals have been positively identified on Mercury's surface. Graphite is thought to be present, but its abundance remains debated (Xu et al., 2024). This lack of information about surface mineralogy generates substantial uncertainty in the interpretation of the surface geochemical data. For example, the composition of the high-magnesium region (HMR) is consistent either with it being formed from high-degree melts or a part of the mantle exhumed by a large impact (Weider et al., 2015; Frank et al. 2017), which have quite different implications for Mercury's evolution. Measuring the mineralogy, and mineral compositions, would distinguish between these two possibilities. Likewise, determining the phase(s) in which sulfur and iron reside at the surface would provide important clues to melting conditions within Mercury (Nittler et al., 2011). Mineralogy also provides constraints on cooling rates and crystallization conditions of magmas. BepiColombo will make thermal IR measurements that will improve our knowledge of mineralogy, though it remains to be seen how diagnostic and quantitative the measurements will be.

c) Interior volatiles

Geological features on Mercury's surface, such as hollows and pyroclastic deposits, as well as MESSENGER geochemical data, indicate the presence of volatiles. Since hollows and pyroclastics represent the most recent changes to Mercury's surface, it implies that **volatile species continued to play an important role in Mercury's evolution, long after its formation and the disappearance of its magma ocean, and there are many unanswered questions.** How did Mercury retain these

volatiles? Are these volatiles evidence that Mercury formed further from the Sun and migrated inward, or were the 'volatile' elements not actually volatile at Mercury's low oxygen fugacity? More detailed analyses of the surface, including both composition and mineralogy are needed, as are experiments to explore volatility of elements under Mercury-like conditions. Better understanding of how volatiles would be retained during magma ocean crystallization, and how they would be mobilized during mantle melting, is also needed.

d) Low-reflectance material

One of the most enigmatic features of Mercury's surface is the low-reflectance material (LRM). LRM covers large areas of the surface and is concentrated in the more ancient, highly cratered terrain (Klima et al., 2018). It is exhumed by impact craters and so appears to be located at depth (Klima et al., 2018; Lark et al., 2023). LRM is thought to contain a few percent graphite (Peplowski et al., 2016), which is a stable igneous phase at Mercury's conditions, and has been postulated to have floated out of the magma ocean to form a floatation crust, analogous to the Moon's feldspathic primary crust (Vander Kaaden et al., 2015). In this case, the LRM may record the earliest stages of Mercury's evolution. Also, hollows often appear to be associated with and formed on LRM (Thomas et al., 2014a; 2016). The origin of hollows and the material they are made of is unclear, but one possibility is that they are sulfide-rich and are formed by sublimation of the sulfides (Blewett et al., 2013; Thomas et al., 2016). If so, this implies that LRM is both C- and S-rich. The southern hemisphere contains the largest concentrations of LRM (Peplowski et al., 2016), and so BepiColombo should provide new constraints on the LRM's origins. Better measurements of surface chemistry and especially mineralogy, particularly from in-situ measurements, would provide key insights into the nature of LRM.

e) Low crustal iron

Mercury's mafic lava surface is low in Fe (2–5 wt%; Nittler et al., 2011) compared with mafic lavas on the Earth, Moon, and Mars (typically 6–15 wt%). This discovery has been taken as an indication of Mercury's low oxygen fugacity. However, Fe solubility in silicate minerals and melts at the estimated fO_2 for Mercury (IW-3 to IW-7) is 0.1 wt.% and below. Therefore, while Mercury's surface is low in Fe, it is an order of magnitude higher than expected (Chabot et al., 2014b)—a major enigma in understanding Mercury's surface composition. **Understanding the origin of Mercury's crustal Fe content will provide fundamental insights into Mercury's evolution.** VNIR spectroscopy data of the surface are also consistent with very-low fO_2 , showing no FeO absorption bands (Izenberg et al., 2014). One possible explanation for Mercury's low-surface Fe abundance and predicted oxygen fugacity is that the surface Fe might be derived from the late delivery of meteorites. Although in this case a corresponding enrichment of Ni should have been detected by XRS, but was not. Alternatively, Mercury's interior may not be as reduced as the surface, and Fe solubility could be higher in melts generated in the mantle and become more reduced by the graphite in the crust as they make their way to the surface (McCubbin et al., 2017). The surface Fe could be in FeS, and not in silicates, although it is not clear how a phase as dense as FeS would be transported to the surface by melts. Better compositional and mineralogical mapping is needed to make progress in understanding Mercury's Fe. BepiColombo will provide improvements in coverage

and spatial resolution, but to fully resolve this knowledge gap analyses of a sample, either from a landed mission or a sample return mission, will be required.

3.3 Investigate the origin and evolution of the polar deposits

a) Distribution and volume

Understanding the distribution and volume of polar ice deposits will provide insights into their origins, as well as to their contribution to Mercury's volatile budget and cycle. Data from both MESSENGER and Earth-based telescopes provide first-order information of the distribution of the deposits (Harmon et al., 2011; Chabot et al., 2014a; 2018), but until BepiColombo arrives, there are little data for the south pole and, due to poor lighting conditions, even the distributions at the north pole are only broadly constrained. The thickness of the ice is also defined by Earth-based radar, and by MESSENGER topographic data (Deutsch et al., 2018; Susorney et al., 2019), but the uncertainty remains high. Models of temperatures within ice-bearing PSRs are consistent with the location of the ice but are under constrained by the low-resolution images and a lack of knowledge of conditions within the PSRs (Chabot et al., 2016).

High-resolution images with enhanced sensitivity (c.f., ShadowCam) or an active light source (c.f., Lunar Flashlight) of the ice deposits are needed from orbit, to better constrain distribution of the deposits at the poles and within craters. Improved topographic data, gravity, reflectance, and thickness (from ground penetrating radar) measurements would provide invaluable constraints. Landed missions and rovers could make local, detailed observations of ice distribution and thickness, and ground-truth remote sensing data.

b) Composition

MESSENGER and Earth-based radar observations provided strong evidence to support the presence of water ice as a major component of Mercury's polar deposits ((Harmon et al., 2011; Chabot et al., 2014a; 2016; 2018). MESSENGER also showed that water ice is not the only volatile present. There are low-reflectance volatiles stable at warmer temperatures, consistent with them being complex organic compounds (Chabot et al., 2016; Delitsky et al., 2017). However, no measurement of the compositions of these low-reflectance volatiles has been made. **Measuring the composition of both the low-reflectance and high-reflectance polar volatiles is key to constraining their source material(s).** Isotopic ratios and speciation along with age constraints (e.g., differences in ice purity, composition, and thickness within and between polar deposits and association to local temperature) can help to determine whether the materials originated from comets vs. asteroids vs. solar wind implantation vs. planetary degassing.

Earth-based radar observations of polar deposit backscatter have provided important constraints on the locations, thicknesses, and purity of the polar deposits (Chabot et al., 2018). However, improvements in, and experimental validation of, radar scattering models and laws for coherent backscatter within planetary-relevant ices are needed to reduce uncertainties in inverting dielectric permittivity from the

measured backscatter. Expanding our library of dielectric properties of planetary-relevant volatiles at radar-relevant wavelengths and at low temperatures is essential to precisely determine the fractions of water vs. other volatiles/contaminants. Element and isotope analyses are needed to constrain the origin of the ice. A landed penetrator experiment, combined with in situ analyses, would offer access to PSR and polar deposit properties, and provide some geochemical and textural information. An active disruption experiment (e.g., LCROSS) would provide new information on volatile composition, thermal depth, and origin. Ultimately, a sample return mission will be required to obtain detailed geochemical and textural data, which is needed to fully characterize the deposits.

c) Volatile transport

Mercury's polar deposits are a laboratory in which to investigate the processes that govern volatile transport, sequestration, and loss on airless bodies (Chabot et al., 2014a; Deutsch et al., 2019). The efficiency of volatile transport can be addressed by modeling and observations. If there is a significant ongoing supply of volatiles (e.g., by solar wind or micrometeorites), then water should be present in the exosphere, particularly at high latitudes close to the dawn terminator. Understanding of the polar deposits could therefore be advanced through a broader investigation of exospheric and ionospheric dynamics and space weathering at Mercury (Delitsky et al., 2017). If the polar deposits are remnants of episodic delivery (e.g., by a comet or asteroid), then the observed distribution of volatiles can help to constrain models of volatile transport and the evolution of short-lived atmospheres following impacts (Deutsch et al., 2018). Relatedly, high-resolution topography and temperature measurements/models would provide improvements to these models, and major constraints on the distribution, abundance, and lifetimes of cold traps. It is also not clear if there are places that once held polar deposits that are now devoid of them. High-resolution imaging and spectroscopy inside PSRs to look for geomorphologic and/or chemical residues of past ices deposits may allow for a better understanding of Mercury's polar volatile cycle.

Measurements of the near-surface solar wind flux and micrometeorite flux with landed missions are important for constraining ongoing supply/modification processes. Improvements in models of depositional processes (e.g., solar wind implantation, impacts) and modification processes (e.g., impact gardening, radiolytic processing) should continue as new observational constraints emerge. Improved radar measurements would provide insight into ice purity as a function of location, and thus, spatially-dependent delivery and modification processes. Understanding the stratigraphy of current polar deposits (and thus, their accumulation and evolutionary histories) may be addressable through radar/microwave sounding or high-resolution imaging.

Finally, thermal models and impact gardening models can provide insight into the lifetime of volatiles. Observations that correlate the presence of volatiles of different composition to environmental factors including temperature, slope, longitude, host crater composition, and incident particle flux can distinguish the relative importance of putative loss processes and their efficiency.

3.4 Explore the history of the intrinsic magnetic field

a) Remanent magnetism

Low-altitude orbital observations by MESSENGER revealed short-wavelength crustal magnetic fields (Johnson et al., 2015). Within the region covered by low-altitude MESSENGER magnetometer data (~35–80°N), much of the crust is at least weakly magnetized. **The minerals that host the crustal magnetization remain unknown, yet their identity is vital for constraining how the magnetization was recorded and its depth extent.** Possible candidates given Mercury's chemically reducing conditions are metallic iron, iron alloys, sulfides, and even carbides. With the low-iron abundance of Mercury's surface some impactors are potential sources for delivering exogenous ferromagnetic material (i.e., metallic Fe-Ni) to the surface. Identifying the carriers of magnetization, and the characteristics of those carriers as a function of planetary surface conditions (e.g., compositional variations, grain size, etc.), as well as determining the geometry of and depth to magnetic sources will permit exploration of the implications for the composition of Mercury's crust and (perhaps) impactors. The crustal field associated with the strongest magnetization is consistent with thermoremanent magnetization and thus, may host a record of the history of Mercury's magnetic field (i.e., present at the time the lavas' solidification). The strongest crustal magnetization is correlated with some (but not all) impact basins and large craters (Hood et al., 2018; Johnson et al., 2018; Galluzzi et al., 2021), particularly those within and around the Caloris basin. **Improved characterization of the crustal field globally is vital for understanding the extent of crustal magnetization and the overall history of the magnetic field** (e.g., a better grasp of the timing of magnetization and ancient dynamo activity).

The presence of a present-day intrinsic magnetic field on Mercury (e.g., Ness et al., 1975; Jackson and Beard, 1977; Whang, 1977; Anderson et al., 2011) **indicates that a convecting liquid outer core remains.** The composition of the solid inner core and liquid outer core are still debated—where Ni, S, C, and Si may play an important role in the composition, density, and melting properties of the core (e.g., Fei and Tao, 2021; Dobrosavljevic et al., 2022; Edmund et al., 2022; Miozzi et al., 2022). Additionally, the composition and physical properties of the core-mantle boundary region remain to be understood. Further experimental and modeling work, hopefully complemented by new mission data from BepiColombo, is needed to improve our understanding of Mercury's core cooling.

The early, long-lived magnetic field suggested by Mercury's crustal magnetization is one of the most informative constraints on Mercury's thermal evolution, since Mercury's dynamo is thought to be generated by a core that is cooling rapidly and/or crystallizing. Both of these scenarios have proven challenging to align with other observational constraints on Mercury's present and past thermal state, such as its small present-day inner core and moderate overall secular cooling. To fully understand the connection between observed crustal remanent magnetization and Mercury's thermal history, it is necessary to develop a deeper understanding of dynamo processes, as well as improved knowledge of the physical properties (e.g., thermal conductivity), composition (e.g. S, Si, C contents) and phase diagrams of potential core materials (especially carbon-bearing alloys). Furthermore, the geodynamic implications of an early dynamo on Mercury must be understood by continuing to integrate

this knowledge with constraints on other facets of its thermal history (volcanism, global contraction) and present-day state (inner core size, core thermal state) (e.g., Davies et al., 2024).

b) Dipole field strength

Mercury's magnetic field is primarily characterized by a dipole aligned with the planet's rotational axis. However, the dipole is not centered at the geographic center of Mercury but is displaced northward by 19.6% of Mercury's reference radius (Alexeev et al., 2010; Anderson et al., 2012). MESSENGER's orbit provided abundant measurements of the magnetic field close to the planet, but only over the northern hemisphere. This data distribution is thus suboptimal for determining the global magnetic power spectrum via spherical harmonics; although local approaches can regionally resolve parts of the spectrum (e.g., Plattner and Johnson, 2021).

The weak dipole field strength and the pronounced axisymmetry of Mercury's magnetic field present significant challenges to standard dynamo theory. Assuming a traditional force balance between Lorentz and Coriolis forces within the core, one would predict a dipole field strength one to two orders of magnitude greater than observed. Moreover, Cowling's theorem (Cowling, 1933) prohibits purely axisymmetric dynamos, further complicating the interpretation of Mercury's magnetic field. Various dynamo models have been proposed to reconcile these observations with core dynamo theory (see (Heyner et al., 2021; Genova et al., 2021 for an overview). To rigorously test these models, particularly in relation to the higher multipole components of the field, more data—especially from the southern hemisphere—are required. The BepiColombo mission, with its Mercury Planetary Orbiter (MPO), is expected to provide critical observations. However, the MPO's pericenter altitude will likely remain above 250 km throughout the mission, even during an extended operational period. To achieve the same level of detail as Earth's magnetic field models and to investigate small-scale crustal magnetic fields, additional close-in measurements would be necessary.

Mercury's dipole offset (Anderson et al., 2011), relative to its size, is the most pronounced among the planets in our solar system. The planet's magnetic field can be represented in two primary ways: either as a single dipole displaced toward the north or as a multipole expansion centered at the geographic center. From a fluid dynamics standpoint, it is difficult to envision a dynamo process that would generate only a single magnetic mode. Dynamo scaling laws suggest that Mercury should lie within the multipolar regime, implying that higher-order magnetic components, beyond the dipole, should be significant. These higher multipoles, due to their rapid geometric decay, are expected to be most evident close to the planetary surface, highlighting the need for close-in measurements.

3.5 Infer long-term effects of variations in exospheric source and loss mechanisms

a) Origin of the exosphere

Mercury is surrounded by a surface-bounded exosphere represented by seven major components: H, He, O, Na, K, Ca, and Mg (Grava et al. 2021). The concentrations of most of these elements are strongly correlated with the effects of different solar phenomena at Mercury's surface, whereas the Ca and Mg exospheres have been connected to impact vaporization and sputtering. However, current models do

not quantitatively explain the observed spatial and temporal variations observed in these elements. **Pathways of material loss from the surface to create each of these exospheric elements are not fully understood.** Improved observations of Mercury's exosphere and improved theoretical and numerical modeling are needed.

The link between meteoroid impacts and different species in Mercury's exosphere has been established thanks to MESSENGER data. BepiColombo is expected to provide a variety of new measurements and constraints that would provide a tighter connection of the Ca, CaO, and Mg exosphere structure to the imprint of the meteoroid influx at Mercury from both the sporadic meteoroid background (Pokorný et al. 2018) and the individual parent bodies such as comet 2P/Encke (Christou et al 2015, 2024).

b) Space weathering processes and rates

Particles, photons, and micrometeorites can desorb material from the surfaces of regolith grains and cause changes in their chemical composition, optical properties, and morphologic structure, cumulatively known as space weathering. Micrometeoroid impacts vaporize regolith grains, produce impact gardening of the regolith, contaminate the surface with exogenic materials, and cause electrostatic effects on surface processes. Photon and electron stimulated desorption (PSD and ESD, respectively) can drive release of Na, K, and H₂O, and potentially other moderately volatile species including Ca and S, through electronic excitations. Solar wind ion impacts lose energy through binary collisions with the target material and release atoms, molecules, and ions from the top-most layers of the solid surface in a process known as sputtering.

Open questions relating to these space weathering effects include: What is the relative importance of each of the above-described space weathering processes for the various surface species found on Mercury? What are the binding energies of volatile materials adsorbed onto the surfaces of regolith grains, and how do these change when the species are incorporated into the crystalline structure of the grains? How are binding energies affected by the presence of voids, cracks, and other surface defects? How do binding energies change the desorption energies of volatile species (and thus their exospheric densities)? What are the delivery rates of volatiles to the poles? How does the temperature of the surface influence the relative importance of the various desorption processes? These questions can be addressed with laboratory space weathering experiments, combined with more detailed observations of spatial and temporal variations in Mercury's exosphere.

4. Investigate processes currently ongoing at Mercury

4.1 Characterize present-day geologic activity

a) Present-day cratering rate

Estimates for the current impact flux at Mercury have been derived using numerous techniques including dynamical calculations (Marchi et al., 2005; Pokorný et al., 2018), extrapolating measurements from the

Moon (Marchi et al., 2009), and by searching for surface changes in spacecraft images (Speyerer et al., 2022). The latter observational analysis identified 19 surface changes that were attributed to the formation of craters >100 m. If this estimate is correct, **the implied crater formation rate is a factor of 1000 times higher than existing production models, necessitating further work to understand the discrepancy between observations and models.**

Understanding the role dust impacts play in shaping Mercury's surface and exosphere is an important ongoing field of work. To date, studies have been conducted to understand the dust population (<10 micron particles) using measurements in the inner solar system from Parker Solar Probe and Solar Orbiter (e.g., Mann et al., 2019; Krüger et al., 2024) and more specifically at Mercury (Krüger et al., 2024). For particle sizes up to 10 micrometers, the Mercury Dust Monitor (MDM) on BepiColombo will provide a direct measurement. In the future, an orbiter hosting a dedicated dust detector with a mass spectrometer (e.g., Sternovsky et al., 2011) could be used to derive particle impact velocity vector, mass, and composition. For particle sizes from 10 micrometers to 1 centimeter, work could be done to indirectly estimate the flux by better understanding the excitation of the Mercury's exosphere via micrometeoroid impacts (Killen and Hahn, 2015; Pokorný et al., 2018). Further work is needed to improve our knowledge of collisional processes between particles, the influence of dust/meteoroid shapes on magnitudes of radiative effects, and hypervelocity chemistry (melting, vaporization, ionization of different species).

For particle sizes from 1 centimeter and above, more insights with change detection (e.g., inter MESSENGER–BepiColombo high-resolution image comparisons) will aid in further characterizing the present-day meteoroid impact flux. Telescopic or orbital observations of impact flashes on Mercury's surface (c.f. lunar observations Suggs et al., 2014) or detection with seismic instruments or infrasound techniques (Silber and Brown, 2018) on a lander could help to estimate the present-day impactor flux, mass, and energy. Additionally, characterizing the current impact rate on Mercury will shed light on the dynamical evolution of the near-Earth orbit (NEO) population into Mercury crossers.

b) Recent/current volcanic activity

Identifying recent effusive volcanism is challenging as it can be difficult to distinguish smooth lava flows from impact melts. Finding volcanic vents would be diagnostic, however locating vents of effusive lavas is often difficult because they tend to self-seal. It is therefore an aim to identify and obtain stereo image pairs of candidate vent areas at the sub-10 m/pixel-scale and **identify and characterize the most recent effusive volcanism** by defining spectrally homogeneous areas as small as about 400 km². Crater counts down to crater diameters of 1 km should be done on these areas to test whether spectral units have different CSFDs and to quantify these as ages using a crater production function. To achieve this aim, high-resolution spectral imaging of smooth plains units is needed, as well as absolute age calibrations that can be achieved via sample return or in situ radiometric dating. In addition, geologic context can help distinguish between small young effusive volcanism and impact melt, but compositional information from X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and visible-to-thermal infrared (VISTIR) spectroscopy will ultimately only provide the important disambiguation.

Mercury has more than 100 candidate sites of explosive eruption. Two of the youngest explosive vents have been dated as Kuiperian (<280 Ma) on the basis of a superposition relationship with crisp craters (Thomas et al., 2014b; Jozwiak et al., 2018). The eruptive lifetime of each explosive vent site is poorly defined, but many vents consist of multiple closely spaced loci of eruption, suggestive of multiple eruptions spaced over perhaps long intervals. Most explosive deposits (faculae) could be a cumulative product of many separate eruptions (Pegg et al. 2021). The composition and rate at which faculae lose their spectral distinctiveness with age remains unknown. It is thus an aim to better define the timing and duration of the explosive eruptions. To achieve this aim, high-resolution imaging can provide fine-scale superpositional relationships and textural differences within compound vents, whereas compositional information via high-resolution XRF and VISTIR spectroscopy and space weathering experiments can provide information on composition and longevity of spectral distinctiveness of faculae.

c) Recent/current tectonic activity

Large thrust fault-related scarps, 100s of km long, crosscut impact craters as old as pre-Tolstojan (> ~4 Ga) but as young as Kuiperian (< 280 Ma). Despite such evidence for a long duration of contraction, it is not known how active tectonics on Mercury are at present (Crane and Klimczak, 2017). The crosscutting of scarps with small craters and very small-scale thrust fault scarps suggests that tectonic activity occurred geologically recently and is perhaps ongoing (Watters et al., 2016). Very small grabens on large, old lobate scarps also suggest long-lived and/or recent tectonism on Mercury (Man et al., 2023). To understand how geologically recent the landforms are, an aim is to understand their spatial and kinematic relations to larger shortening structures, and what process(es) drive their formation. Another aim is to identify the current rate of tectonic deformation to specify how tectonically active Mercury is at present.

The mechanisms driving the tectonic activity on Mercury are not fully quantified. It is crucial to understand the respective roles of continuing global contraction, topographic relaxation, thermally and tidally induced deformation, seismic surface modification leading to mass wasting, and even local-scale deformation from magma ascent or impact bombardment.

Understanding the relative contribution of these processes will provide insights into the evolution of Mercury's interior. Characterization of relationships between tectonic features and impact craters, cataloging of indicators of recent surface change such as landslides and boulder trails from higher-resolution-than-currently-available images, and determination of potential surface changes between data from MESSENGER, BepiColombo, and future orbiters are approaches that can indicate tectonic sources of geologic activity. Furthermore, using tectonic observations to inform modeling of the potential for seismicity from Mercury's solid body (solar) tides—suggested to be as much as 17 times larger than those on the Moon (Van Holst and Jacobs, 2003)—as well as modeling coseismic slip on thrust faults will inform current deformation rates. A Mercury lander containing one (or more) seismometer(s) would ultimately provide information on deformation rates by measuring magnitudes, frequencies, and sources of quakes.

Finally, the investigation of Mercury's tectonic and volcanic activity requires understanding of its interior, especially the composition and structure of the silicate portion of the planet. New insight from

BepiColombo's instruments as well as new laboratory measurements on crust and mantle analogs and numerical modeling will help to constrain the mineralogy and thermal state of the silicate portion. For instance, induction data can be used to obtain an electrical conductivity-depth profile of the mantle (Genova et al., 2021), which can be used to place constraints on the mineralogy and thermal state (e.g., Pommier et al., 2025). Elucidating the interior of the planet is necessary to model the different deformation processes and related volcanism that shaped the surface.

d) Hollows

Although much progress has been made in understanding hollows, how they form remains an open question. It is generally agreed that the hollows are young (Blewett et al., 2011, 2013), that sublimation or space weathering processes are involved in hollow formation (Blewett et al., 2011, 2013; Vaughan et al., 2012; Phillips et al., 2021), and that hollows are associated with Mercury's Low Reflectance Material (LRM) (Blewett et al., 2013; Thomas et al., 2014a). Most hollows occur within impact craters or material excavated by impacts (Thomas et al., 2014a; Blewett et al., 2018); however, whether impacts simply excavate material or play some additional role, such as providing necessary heat or melt products, is unknown. It has also been proposed that ejecta blocks from Caloris that have been modified by long-term and ongoing mass wasting had substantial volatile contents and may be related to hollows (Wright et al., 2020). A first aim is to determine the identity of the volatile-bearing phase that is lost in the hollow-formation process. High-resolution compositional and reflectance orbital measurements of hollows and LRM could help to unveil their composition and relationship to one another. Landed elemental (e.g., sulfur and carbon) and mineralogical (e.g., sulfide, carbide) measurements will be critical for understanding the volatile-bearing phase. A second aim is to constrain the mechanism by which hollows form. High-resolution images of hollow morphology could shed light on hollow formation. High-resolution image coverage of Mercury's southern hemisphere would allow a mapping of the global distribution of hollows and their associations with other landforms. A third aim is to constrain the ages, formation timescales, and growth-rates of hollows. Higher resolution imaging of the surface would determine the ages of host units and could reveal "fossil" hollows (not bright compared to their surroundings). Change-detection imaging (visible or radar) of hollows could illuminate whether hollows are actively growing and at what rate.

e) Polar deposits

The polar ice deposits in Mercury PSRs have few craters and so appear to be recent and/or active features. In addition, their covering of dark, possibly organic, material appears to correlate closely with the extent of the permanently shadowed areas (Chabot et al., 2014a). Potential current processes acting on the deposits include sublimation/de-sublimation, micrometeoroid impact, space weathering, ion implantation and interaction with the magnetic field.

To improve our understanding of the processes currently affecting the polar deposits, along with their current accumulation and loss rates, a number of key measurements are needed. These include detailed measurements of polar thermal environments, measurements of solar wind flux at multiple locations (including at latitudes where water ice is exposed at the surface and at latitudes where water ice is

insulated by a layer of low-albedo materials), and measurements of the ongoing regolith gardening rates. High-resolution measurements of the gravity field would provide key insights into the distribution of ice, and better measurements of magnetic fields at the poles would improve constraints on ice formation and loss processes. A lander (even one not at the polar regions) would provide key constraints on ongoing activity. High-resolution images, reflectance measurements, and topographic measurements of the polar deposits are also important, particularly if they can be made repeatedly over long timespans, to directly measure changes and rates of changes. Additionally, measurements of polar deposit purity as a function of depth (e.g., by radar sounding) would provide insight into ice evolutionary history.

A variety of experiments and model improvements would also improve our understanding of ongoing processes at the polar deposits, including experiments and models of space weathering rates at Mercury's polar conditions, experiments of cometary-like volatiles to test what low-reflectance volatiles may form after exposure to Mercury-like environmental conditions, and experiments to determine how thermal lag deposits may develop and evolve in Mercury-like conditions.

4.2 Investigate magnetospheric dynamics

a) Generation of the current magnetic field

The global magnetic field of Mercury is likely generated by a convection-driven dynamo in the core (e.g., Christensen, 2006) that is thought to have operated early in the planet's history (~ 3.7–3.9 billion years; Johnson et al., 2015). Using magnetic and geodetic measurements, it has been suggested that the metallic core is at least partially liquid at present (e.g., Steinbrügge et al., 2021). Core cooling models have shown that iron snow is unlikely to occur in Mercury's core, and the growth of a solid inner core is the only expected crystallization mechanism (Knibbe and van Westrenen, 2018; Davies et al., 2024). Models that best reproduce the existing observational constraints are obtained for a layered core made of a molten outer portion, composed of a thick thermally stable layer and a convecting region where the dynamo is generated, and a solid inner core. The presence of a hypothetical molten FeS layer atop the core would have minimal effect on Mercury's long-term thermal and magnetic evolution (Davies et al., 2024). The size of the expected solid inner core is debated (up to 1500 km; e.g., Genova et al., 2019), partly due to the lack of constraints on core chemistry, and new data from BepiColombo's Mercury Orbiter Radio Science Experiment (MORE) (less et al., 2021) are expected to shed light on the structure and evolution of the core.

Characterizing the compositional and physical properties of Mercury's core is key to modeling core dynamics and the origin of the magnetic field. Information about the chemistry of the metallic core has been obtained by the combination of surface composition data and laboratory experiments. The low-Fe and high-S contents in mercurian lavas suggest that the core formed under highly reducing conditions (e.g., McCubbin et al., 2012). At these fO_2 conditions, high-pressure and high-temperature experiments showed that only small amounts (<~2.0 wt.%) of sulfur are expected in the core, whereas Si could alloy with Fe in significant proportions (>10 wt.%; e.g., Knibbe and van Westrenen, 2018; Goossens et al., 2022). A non-negligible amount of Ni (several wt.%) is expected, based on iron meteorite cosmochemistry, and substantial amounts of C might also be present in the core (e.g., Vander

Kaaden et al., 2020). In addition, partitioning experiments of Si between liquid and solid Fe alloys indicated that large amounts of silicon are expected to partition to the solid inner core (e.g., Tao and Fei, 2021).

Current understanding of the physical properties of Mercury's core rests largely on MESSENGER-based determinations of the rotational state (i.e., amplitude of the physical libration and the orientation of the planet), the second-degree harmonics of the gravity field (e.g., Margot et al 2018, Bertone et al., 2021) and laboratory measurements of the physical properties (e.g., Pommier et al., 2019). Better measurements of Mercury's gravity field, along with higher precision topography would greatly advance our understanding of the origin of Mercury's magnetic field, as would experimental studies focused on the relevant core compositions and conditions.

b) Magnetic reconnection

Mercury and Earth both have reconnection-driven magnetospheres, with energy and momentum from the solar wind driving the circulation of magnetic flux through the system. The relative reconnection rates on the dayside and in the magnetotail govern the change in open magnetic flux content of the system, and thus are important parameters for describing the global magnetospheric dynamics (Imber and Slavin, 2017; Slavin et al., 2021), the distribution and acceleration of magnetospheric plasma (e.g. Dewey et al., 2018), and the location of particle precipitation to the surface (e.g. Poh et al., 2016; Lindsay et al., 2016; Raines et al., 2022). Although MESSENGER rarely observed reconnection sites directly (e.g., Zhong et al., 2018), it recorded ample evidence of the frequency and importance of reconnection to Mercury's magnetosphere. **Due to the single-point nature of MESSENGER's in situ plasma and magnetic field observations, many outstanding features of magnetic reconnection in Mercury's magnetosphere remain**, including: the number and locations of simultaneous reconnection sites at the magnetopause and/or in the magnetotail; the influence of planetary ions on reconnection occurrence and strength; the relative importance of low-latitude Kelvin-Helmholtz waves for plasma entry and flux circulation compared to magnetic reconnection; the relation between reconnection and dawn-dusk asymmetries; particle energization (both ion and electron) directly from reconnection and from reconnection products.

c) Induction effects

The small dimensions of Mercury's magnetosphere and the large volume occupied by the planet's conducting core result in electromagnetic coupling between the planet's interior and its magnetosphere. Since Mercury lacks an ionosphere, changes in the external magnetic field directly affect the planet as, in response, inductive currents form on the surface of Mercury's highly conducting core to oppose these changes. Induction currents introduce additional magnetic flux to the magnetosphere that, like the intrinsic magnetic field, can undergo dynamic processes like magnetic reconnection. **The effect of induction and its role in the coupling between Mercury's magnetosphere and interior are not well understood.** Initial studies of induction using MESSENGER data have confirmed annual and episodic changes in the planet's axial dipole magnetic moment due to changes in solar wind dynamic

pressure, with a few-percent change due to annual dynamic pressure variation (Johnson et al., 2016) and effects as strong as ~50–100% due to solar wind transients (e.g., Slavin et al., 2014). However, other causes for induction effects, such as those related to magnetotail current systems and dynamics, remain unconfirmed. Further, the consequences of the additional magnetic flux in the magnetosphere generated by induction currents remain poorly constrained. During high-pressure events, the flux added to the dayside helps to prevent the collapse of the dayside magnetosphere to the surface of the planet. However, strong magnetopause reconnection can transport this flux to the magnetotail, eroding the dayside magnetosphere anyway.

The interplay between induction and reconnection, and their effects on the magnetosphere's structure and content, require further investigation. While induction is present at many solar system objects, such as the Galilean moons, only Mercury and Ganymede are known to possess both global magnetic fields and at least weakly conducting interiors. As Ganymede is deeply embedded in Jupiter's magnetosphere, Mercury is a unique place to study induction effects as its magnetosphere is subject to the more variable solar wind. Expected data from BepiColombo's MPO-MAG instrument have the potential to answer several questions related to Mercury's magnetosphere (Heyner et al., 2021).

d) Dawn-dusk asymmetries

Mercury's magnetosphere exhibits differences between its duskside and dawnside in the characteristics and dynamics of its plasma and magnetic field. These dawn-dusk asymmetries are present throughout the system, but are pronounced in the magnetotail, where, for example, the dawnside means current sheet thickness is greater (e.g., Poh et al., 2017; Rong et al., 2018), the plasma density is higher (e.g., Korth et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2020), and signatures related to magnetic reconnection are more frequent than on the duskside magnetotail (e.g., Sun et al., 2016; Smith et al., 2017; Dewey et al., 2017; Dewey et al., 2020). Some dawn-dusk asymmetries are similar to Earth, however, others are opposite in their dawn-dusk preference (see, e.g., a review by Sun et al., 2022). Characterization of dawn-dusk asymmetries to date has relied on statistical accumulation of MESSENGER observations within the magnetosphere. While these accumulations describe average local properties, they integrate over the time history of the system, lack context of solar wind driving, and compare temporally and spatially distant measurements. As a result, **the origins and consequences of these asymmetries remain unresolved.**

One aim is therefore to understand the physical origins of the magnetosphere's dawn-dusk asymmetries, while another aim is to determine the influence of these asymmetries on the magnetosphere's internal dynamics. Characterization of relationships between dawn-dusk asymmetries and external solar wind driving conditions; comparison of dayside and nightside magnetosphere mass, energy, and momentum budgets and the transfer of these quantities throughout the system and with the solar wind; resolution of meso-scale dynamics (~0.1 of Mercury's reference radius) and constraining their contribution to global magnetosphere configuration; and tracing of particles and field lines through the magnetosphere as a function of magnetospheric state can each help to resolve the origins and effects of dawn-dusk asymmetries. Such activities rely on simultaneous multi-point in situ measurements within or across

magnetospheric regions, knowledge of upstream solar wind conditions, and comparison between global simulations and localized spacecraft measurements.

e) Magnetospheric currents

Mercury's major magnetospheric currents generally resemble those of Earth, but there are significant differences in current closure at Mercury due to its lack of a conducting ionosphere. The major current systems at Mercury include magnetopause current, cross-magnetotail current sheet, a ring-like current about the planet, and field-aligned currents. At the dayside magnetopause, a Chapman-Ferraro current separates the closed dayside magnetosphere field from the magnetosheath. Mercury's magnetopause is more conducive to reconnection than Earth's, including instances of symmetric reconnection, and the resulting differences in magnetopause current strength and coherence compared to Earth's are currently unknown. In the magnetotail, the dawn-to-dusk cross-tail current sheet is a consequence of the elongation of nightside field lines. There is some evidence for bifurcation of this current sheet (Al Asad et al., 2021), but the origins and consequences of this bifurcation are not well understood. Close to the planet, trapped particles injected from the magnetotail into the dipole-dominated region of the magnetosphere gradient-curvature drift about the planet. Although the existence and frequency of drift paths remain under debate, recent work has suggested a sufficient amount of plasma drifts to form the equivalent of an Earth-like ring current (Shi et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022). However, the direction and primary current carriers cannot currently be reconciled. At the dayside, this current may close about equatorial dayside, but during moderate magnetosphere forcing the current is expected to split into the northern and southern hemispheres in a Shabansky-like configuration.

The current systems at Mercury that are least likely to resemble Earth's are its field-aligned current (FAC) systems. Since Mercury lacks a conducting atmosphere, the interior of the planet is expected to provide necessary closure for these types of current systems. While the exact mechanics and location of current closure in the planet require further constraints, conceptual models suggest the currents flow radially through the resistive crust and mantle, and close at the highly conductive core-mantle boundary. Current closure over the core and the resistive crust/mantle imposes constraints on temporally-variable FACs. MESSENGER observations in the magnetotail suggest a substorm current wedge may form that connects the near-tail region to the planetary interior (e.g., Dewey et al., 2020) but the small spatiotemporal scales of the magnetosphere and the resistive regolith hamper the formation of this system compared to Earth. The frequency and similarity of a substorm current wedge at Mercury remain open. In addition to transient FACs, Mercury's magnetosphere possesses a more permanent Region-1 style current that was consistently observed by MESSENGER over Mercury's northern pole (e.g., Anderson et al., 2014, 2018). These large-scale polar FACs are quasi-stationary and omnipresent. The exact origins of this system at Mercury are unknown, but flow shear interior to the magnetopause near the terminator is a possible mechanism. A Region-2 style FAC system has not been observed in the MESSENGER data to date. However, it is expected to exist to complete the Dungey cycle by transporting closed magnetotail field lines to the dayside. New observations of the magnetic field and its evolution with time are required.

f) Flux rope formation

Flux ropes (FRs) are helical bundles of magnetic flux that form between magnetic reconnection sites and are convected away from their location of formation by a combination of magnetic tension forces and dominant plasma flows in the system. Flux ropes at Mercury have been observed by MESSENGER to form in the magnetotail current sheet and along the dayside magnetopause. Dayside magnetopause flux ropes are also known as flux transfer events (FTEs) and are observed moving anti-sunward along the magnetopause where they may transport significant quantities of magnetic flux from the dayside magnetopause into the magnetotail (e.g. Imber et al., 2014).

'Flux transfer event showers' appear to be a phenomenon unique to Mercury (Slavin et al., 2012) and consist of hundreds of FTEs observed over very short time periods. While individual FTEs within the showers were resolved by MESSENGER's magnetometer, their small spatial scale (and corresponding short timescale as they passed over the spacecraft) has limited analysis from plasma observations. These magnetic field observations suggest that FTEs may play a significant or even dominant role in flux transport from Mercury's dayside magnetosphere to the magnetotail. However, without corresponding detailed plasma observations, **questions remain as to the role of FTEs in flux and particle transport, the location of particle precipitation to the planetary surface and subsequent contribution to the generation of the exosphere, and the storage and dissipation of energy within Mercury's magnetosphere.** Observations of the magnetic field over longer time periods with improved coverage are needed.

g) Effect of solar events on the system

Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections (ICMEs) have the strongest effect on Mercury's magnetosphere of any solar events. They typically bring significant increases in plasma flux and magnetic field strength. They mainly drive the magnetosphere via two mechanisms: increased dayside magnetopause reconnection and increased solar wind dynamic pressure. When dayside reconnection dominates, significant magnetic flux is stripped from the dayside magnetosphere and loaded into the magnetotail (Imber and Slavin, 2017), stimulating magnetic reconnection across the central current sheet and increasing magnetospheric circulation. In extreme cases, this erosion of the dayside magnetic field could expose substantial portions of Mercury's dayside surface to direct solar wind impact (Slavin et al., 2019). When pressure dominates, the whole magnetosphere is squeezed, leading to an increase in dayside magnetosphere field strength from magnetic induction on the core (Slavin et al., 2014). The net result can be similar to the reconnection-dominated events: in extreme cases portions of the dayside surface can be exposed to direct solar wind impact. Increased solar wind sputtering likely increases the density of the neutral exosphere and heavy ion content of the magnetosphere (Sun et al., 2022), as well as the space weathering of the surface (Domingue et al., 2015). The combination of the two BepiColombo orbiters will provide two-point measurements that will greatly improve understanding of these events compared with the single-spacecraft measurements of MESSENGER. MPO will continuously monitor near-planet conditions with its lower, nearly circular orbit while Mio will either be upstream monitoring the solar wind or deep in the magnetotail monitoring loading and tail reconnection.

Two other classes of solar events have an indirect and likely much smaller effect on Mercury's magnetosphere: Solar Energetic Particle (SEP) events and solar extreme ultraviolet (EUV) flares. SEP events have been shown to rain energetic electrons down onto Mercury's polar cap (Gershman et al., 2015a). Solar flares cause increases in photon-stimulated desorption of material from the surface as well as likely produce more planetary ions in the magnetosphere, which may precipitate back on to the surface at higher energies. Both of these effects likely lead to more sputtering of neutrals and ions from the surface, but evidence of this effect has not been reported. Future observations using multiple spacecraft are needed to improve our understanding of the Sun's influence on the magnetosphere.

4.3 Understand exospheric and magnetospheric source and loss processes

a) Magnetospheric ions

Because Mercury's exosphere is collisionless, magnetospheric ion dynamics are completely decoupled from exospheric neutrals. The primary sources of magnetospheric ions are entry of the solar wind through dayside magnetopause reconnection and photoionization of exospheric neutrals (Zurbuchen et al., 2008; 2011; Raines et al., 2013). Much smaller quantities likely come from ionization of material from surface micrometeoroid impacts in the hot vaporization cloud (Pokorný et al., 2017; 2018) as well as charge exchange of exospheric neutrals with solar wind protons in the magnetosheath or cusps, though there are currently no measurements to conclusively support either of these cases.

Magnetospheric ions are lost primarily through magnetospheric circulation and kinetic processes. Following magnetic reconnection in the central plasma sheet, as part of Dungey Cycle circulation, ions are carried by helical magnetic structures called plasmoids down the magnetotail and back into the solar wind. Plasma is also carried toward the nightside of the planet by this process, with some being lost to precipitation on the nightside surface through the plasma sheet horns or possibly even across the entire nightside during very active times (Glass et al., 2022). While plasmoids have been observed (Slavin et al., 2008; DiBraccio et al., 2015), estimates of the plasma lost via this process have not been made. The retained ions will tend to drift around Mercury's night side toward the dusk terminator. Mercury's weak magnetic field results in a very small magnetosphere (Slavin et al., 2007), where, on the dayside, the distance between the magnetopause and the planetary surface is often the same scale as ion gyroradii. A large portion of ions drifting through this space will be lost by gyrating either into the planet's surface (precipitation) or into the magnetopause (magnetopause shadowing). The significance of this kinetic process increases with increasing ion energy and mass, so that planetary ions, such as Na^+ , which have gyroradii more than 20 times that of protons at the same energy, can pass through this space only at the lowest energies, 100s of eV (Raines et al., 2014). This effect can be observed in several kinetic models of Mercury, with some showing ions able to circulate all the way around the dayside magnetosphere and thus constituting at least a partial ring current, as well as observations that are consistent with this interpretation (Shi et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022; Hadid et al., 2024). Ions in this region as well as further down the magnetotail can also be lost through the Kelvin-Helmholtz instability, where the differing flow speeds across the magnetopause boundary can cause vortices to form which expel magnetosphere plasma into the magnetosheath (Sundberg et al., 2010; 2012; Liljeblad et al., 2014; Gershman et al.,

2015b, Aizawa et al., 2020). Since magnetosheath plasma is also brought in via this process, it also constitutes a source as well.

More complete observations for all these processes are required to fully understand dependencies on properties such as ion mass and energy. Furthermore, quantitative estimates of source and loss rates for these processes are needed to understand the mass balance for both the magnetosphere and the exosphere.

b) Distributions of neutral and ionized species and their temporal / spatial variations

A key discrepancy exists between measurements of Mercury's exosphere made from the Earth-based telescopes as compared to those made from orbit. Ground-based observations show substantial spatial variability in the exosphere, including transition between a single peak in brightness centered around the equator and a double peak structure, with peaks at high latitudes (Mangano et al., 2015). This variability appears to be at least partially correlated with markers of magnetospheric activity, when compared with in situ plasma and magnetic field measurements from MESSENGER (Orsini et al., 2018). Orbital measurements from MESSENGER's Ultraviolet and Visible Spectrometer (UVVS), in contrast, showed a steadier exosphere where no clear correlation with magnetospheric activity has yet been found (Cassidy et al., 2015). Some of these differences may be attributed to the different regions measured by each observer. Ground-based telescopes can see the entire Earth-facing hemisphere, while MESSENGER data are derived from measurements around the Mercury equator, where they were of highest quality due to viewing effects. BepiColombo carries several instruments that will measure neutral exospheric species in different ways and from different locations than MESSENGER was able and should shed light on this discrepancy.

Ionized exospheric species, often called planetary ions, were observed by MESSENGER concentrated in several key areas: the northern magnetospheric cusp (Zurbuchen et al., 2011; Raines et al., 2014; Sun et al., 2022), the central plasma sheet (Raines et al., 2013; Gershman et al., 2014), and along the magnetopause in conjunction with Kelvin-Helmholtz waves (Sundberg et al., 2012; Aizawa et al., 2020). In most cases, these ions were observed in approximately the 0.5–10 keV/e range, representing ions that have already undergone some energization process. When created from photoionization, these ions have energies of ~ 1 eV or less, which is well below the lower energy range (~ 50 eV) of the MESSENGER UVVS instrument. These very-low-energy populations are expected to exist at least in the dayside magnetosphere and cusp but may well exist in the central plasma sheet. Modeling has shown that ~ 1 eV ions in the cusp can be accelerated by drift through the curved magnetic field structure to end up in the central plasma sheet at the observed keV energy range (Delcourt, 2013). Observations of low-energy planetary ion populations could be used to complete the picture of the life cycle of planetary ions at Mercury, from their origin from photoionization at ~ 1 eV through acceleration to keV energies and eventual loss. The two BepiColombo spacecraft will be well-positioned to make these measurements both near the planet (< 1 Mercury radius) and the more distant magnetotail (> 4 Mercury radii).

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